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EFFECTS OF PHONICS SEQUENCING INSTRUCTION PROGRAMME ON BRAILLE READING AND WRITING SKILLS ACQUISITION OF PUPILS WITH VISUAL IMPAIRMENT IN GINDIRI, PLATEAU STATE

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Abstract: This study examined the effects of Phonics Sequencing Instruction Programme (PSIP) on reading and writing skills of pupils with visual impairment in the School for the Blind Children, Gindiri, Plateau State. The specific objective of the study was, to ascertain the phonics sequencing instruction Programme mean scores on the braille reading skills of the lower basic three pupils with visual impairments in the experimental and control groups, and the second is to determine the phonics sequencing instruction programme mean scores on the Braille writing skills of the lower basic three pupils with visual impairments in the experimental and control groups. Two hypotheses were formulated and tested at the 0.05 level of significance. The study adopted the pre-test, post-test control group experimental design. Through the purposive sampling technique, 10 lower basic three pupils with visual impairment in the School for the Blind Children, Gindiri, were selected to form the sample size for the study. The instrument for data collection was adapted Literacy Skill Acquisition Test in Braille, as the original text was in print form. Inferential statistics of Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to test the two postulated hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that the phonics sequencing instruction programme improves the reading and writing skills of pupils with visual impairment. The study concluded that there was a significant difference in post-test reading acquisition between the experimental and control groups. Also, a significant difference was found in the post-test writing skills between the experimental and control groups. Thus, it was recommended that the phonics sequencing instruction programme (PSIP) be integrated into the curriculum to enhance reading and writing skills for pupils with visual impairment in all special schools.

Keywords: Phonics Sequencing Instruction Programme, Braille Reading Skills, Braille Writing Skills, Pupils with Visual Impairment

Background of the Study

Sight is a fundamental sense required for achieving academic excellence and living a balanced lifestyle. Pupils with visual impairments are those whose sense of sight is impaired. There are two categories of visual impairment: low vision and total blindness. Those with low vision are pupils who rely on their residual sight to enable them to read large print, while those who are totally blind rely on braille as their primary medium of reading and writing. Hence, visual information is important in helping pupils with visual impairments to observe and interpret their environment (Kapur, 2017). Reduced visual acuity makes it difficult for pupils with visual impairments to recognize and distinguish Braille letters, words, and symbols like their sighted counterparts, thereby making learning challenging for them. This has resulted in poor Braille literacy skills among pupils with visual impairments, as they strive for the acquisition of reading and writing skills. Pupils with visual impairments count words when reading; they lack speed and comprehension of what they are reading. They are poor at Braille, with a negative attitude towards Braille, which makes Braille reading decrease among pupils with visual impairments in primary schools.

For pupils with visual impairments, braille reading involves processes, and each letter of the alphabet is formed from a group of braille dots. The pupil needs to learn the dot combinations and shapes for each letter by feeling them tactually. They go on to learn the names of the letters for the purpose of using phonemes for reading the sounds of the letters. Tactual perception is not as common as the use of sight. Therefore, beginning reading with pupils who have visual impairments using other methods, such as whole word, results in a lack of easy prediction of what is ahead while reading. Synthetic phonics or the direct method would be useful for a pupil with visual impairments in reading Braille.

Reading involves listening and understanding what is printed or written on the page. Reading level involves the level of acquisition and understanding displayed in a given text or manuscript. It is gaining word meaning, to which pupils with visual impairments can figure out the meaning from a passage or construct meaning out of a text. The purpose of reading in print and braille is the same. According to Wang and Zhou (2022), reading is a fundamental skill that enables individuals with visual impairments to access information, participate fully in society, and achieve their academic and professional goals. Above all, in modern schools today, a good reading level is the most important avenue to effective learning and literacy skills. Reading skills are interrelated with the total educational process and academic success; they require sound and high reading skills in pupils with visual impairments.

Writing skills, which is Brailing for persons with visual impairment, are the art of making words with a pen or writing material (slate and stylus or braille machine). It is a process of spelling words, creating stories, and making symbols where necessary. Brailing is a complex symbolic representation of a person's thoughts, points of view, and images. When pupils with visual impairments write (braille), attempts to make embossed images and graphic symbols from oral symbols are exhibited. Teachers should always emphasize writing simultaneously with other literacy skills; in other words, it should be taught through other literacy skills. Braille should not be taught separately as if it exists independently, it should be integrated into braille writing and other literacy skills like reading. This will enable Pupils with visual impairments to develop a more comprehensive understanding of literacy. They should be encouraged to braille as they are being taught to read or speak, also for them to practice Braille regularly by encouraging them to copy words in Braille, read what they copied, and discuss it.

Braille literacy skills empower, enlighten, and liberate pupils with visual impairments towards both educational and physical development. As part of the right to education of pupils with visual impairments, literacy skills improve pupils' lives by expanding their didactic capabilities, which in the long run will certainly reduce poverty, increase participation in school, and the larger society. Literacy skills affect the health and sustainability of pupils with visual impairments.

Kilpatrick (2020) posited that literacy skills are the foundation or basis for all other academic knowledge and skills, as they provide the tools for accessing, understanding, and communicating information across the curriculum. The relevance of Braille literacy skills to pupils with visual impairments can be seen in their intellectual soundness, literate confidence, apt learning aptitudes, academic self-assurance, and self-satisfaction. Braille literacy skills acquisition is the basis and measures that involve scores, and it is the scores that determine the acquisition of literacy skills and eventually academic performance. Frequent failure in school by pupils with visual impairments can be traced to inadequate Braille literacy skills or poor Braille literacy acquisition, though there have been efforts to use interventions, techniques, approaches, and various teaching methods, with little or no success. The consequences of poor Braille literacy include poor academic achievement, feelings of being ostracized from academia, low self-esteem, shame, fear, and powerlessness, which have negative effects on pupils with visual impairments. Braille Literacy skills acquisition of pupils with visual impairments refers to their ability to read and write Braille effectively despite their visual limitations. These pupils may use alternative methods such as Braille or assistive technology to access and engage with written material.

The phonics sequencing instruction programme is a method used to improve students' acquisition of literacy skills. The performance of pupils with visual impairments determines their progress in academic and non-academic areas, despite the challenges posed by their visual impairments. Research suggests that pupils with visual impairments often struggle to achieve literacy proficiency, with studies indicating a strong correlation between visual impairments and poor Braille literacy acquisition. American Foundation for the Blind (AFB) (2020) asserted that pupils with visual impairments are faced with significant challenges in literacy skills development, particularly in reading and writing. Pupils with visual impairments struggle with braille writing skills, typing, reading text, comprehending the subject matter, and answering the questions asked during assignments, tests, and examinations (Andreason, 2015, & Leli, 2017). Loh, Prem-Senthil, and Constable (2023), in their research, posited that visual impairments cause delays in literacy acquisition and phonological processing in young children. Pupils with visual impairments often experience delays in reading speed, but not necessarily in reading ability.

The Phonics Sequencing Instruction Programme (PSIP) is the order or arrangement in which phonics sounds and skills are coached or taught. It involves training, counsel, suggestions, directives, persuasions, activities, and therapy for pupils with visual impairments to enhance their literacy skills. PSIP is a systematic procedure for inculcating sound relationships between letters. and their sounds (phonemes), in addition to the awareness of sounds of words (blends), spoken language, or articulation. The word sequencing implies that one thing follows another. The first awareness is the pre-alphabetic principle (relationships between written letters and spoken sounds), and the second alphabetic principle is the foundational skill the child must master to become a successful reader. Hence, letters are taught with their corresponding sounds from simple to complex. Phonics instruction means the method of teaching pupils to read by correlating sounds with symbols in an alphabetic writing system. It is a method of teaching pupils to read Braille, based on learning the sounds that letters represent; it is a method of Braille reading that emphasizes the relationship between letters and sounds. The logic in this method is that the pupils learn Braille letter-sound relationships in phonics and make

connections between Braille letters and speech sounds (phonemes) (Accelerated Christian Education (ACE), 2015).

Phonemes (speech sounds) are blended with constructed words, then phrases and sentences. When pupils with visual impairments learn letter-sound relationships in phonics, they are making connections between printed letters (graphemes) and speech sounds (phonemes). Machin, McNally, and Viarengo (2018) further describe the steps to follow with synthetic phonics, which start with teaching phonemes and then progress to teaching full words. It always starts with teaching phonics, beginning with instruction on about forty-four (44) phonemes and graphemes in the English language. The first stage of instruction usually involves the repetition of phonemes. As pupils progress and become competent with each phoneme, the teacher focuses on blending phonemes to build words. When pupils know the single phonemes (a, b, c, d, e, ...) and some basic two-letter phonemes (at, it, in), they can start blending them to form words like: cat, mat, fin, hit, sit. Synthetic phonics, therefore, often gets the nickname of the “blending and building” approach.

The capacity to write is related to pupils with visual impairments at age-related developmental stages. Pupils with visual impairments tend to read more slowly and make more substitution errors than mispronunciation errors (Bosman et al., 2006). There is no clear agreement on the precise chronological/mental age or particular developmental level that pupils with visual impairments must attain before they are ready to learn to write/braille. Without writing/braille skills, pupils with visual impairments cannot learn the contents of textbooks, which is the reason why many Nigerian primary school pupils with visual impairments do not progress satisfactorily at school.

Pupils with visual impairments are exposed to the names of the letters of the alphabet and the Braille word signs; they struggle to connect letters to form words and sentences. It is because of the issues discussed above that the researcher found it necessary and motivated to research into the Effects of Phonics Sequencing Instruction Programme on Literacy Skills Acquisition of Pupils with Visual Impairments in Gindiri, Plateau State, Nigeria.

Statement of Problem

Pupils with visual impairments often face significant challenges in acquiring literacy skills, particularly in phonics sequencing, which is a fundamental component of Braille reading and writing. The Phonics Sequencing Instruction Programme is not practiced in lower basic schools, which makes reading challenging for pupils with visual impairment. Despite the importance of phonics sequencing instruction, there is a dearth of research on the effectiveness of phonics sequencing instruction programmes specifically designed for pupils with visual impairments. As a result, educators and policymakers lack evidence-based guidance on how best to support the literacy development of pupils with visual impairments, potentially leading to persistent literacy acquisition gaps and limited opportunities for these pupils to reach their full academic and personal potential. When they cannot read and braille well, they become discouraged and frustrated. Which may result in poor performance on standardised tests, increased truancy, and other negative reactions, all of which can have major or long-lasting precautions.

The poor literacy skills acquisition of pupils with visual impairments may be attributed to various factors, which includes, the use of ineffective teacher-centered methods like the chalk and talk approach, teachers’ attitude towards teaching pupils with visual impairments, lack of interest and negative attitude of pupils towards literacy skill tasks, age of on-set of visual impairments, as well as lack of adequate instructional materials. These result in poor listening, speaking, reading, and Braille writing, and may lead to many of the pupils with visual impairments dropping out of school as a result

of repeated failure. Moreover, due to their inability to see, pupils with visual impairments cannot see what the teacher writes on the board; as such, pupils with visual impairments tend to participate passively in class, which leads to poor acquisition and increased truancy.

Otana (2018) reported that 80% of pupils with visual impairments often score poorly in literacy skills tasks, with scores less than 40%. While the National Centre for Educational Statistics (2019) stated that pupils with visual impairments had an average reading score of 34 points lower than their sighted peers on the National Assessment of Educational Progress (NAEP), with 64% scoring below the 50th percentile. UNESCO (2005) highlights a decline in literacy skills acquisition of pupils with visual impairments in Nigeria, while research in special education and rehabilitation sciences suggests that learners with special educational needs have unsatisfactory literacy skills acquisition.

The Federal Government of Nigeria has been striving to improve literacy skills outcomes for pupils with visual impairments by addressing issues of employment of more English teachers, training and retraining of teachers, organising extra lessons for pupils, and the use of different teaching methods, among others. This study aims to answer the broad question: What are the effects of phonics sequencing instruction programmes on literacy skills acquisition of pupils with visual impairments in Gindiri, Plateau State, Nigeria?

Objectives of the study

This study aims to investigate the effects of the Phonics Sequencing Instruction Programme (PSIP) on Braille reading and writing skills of lower basic three pupils with visual impairments in Gindiri, Plateau State, Nigeria. The specific objectives of this study are to:

1. Ascertain the phonics sequencing instruction programme on Braille reading skill of the lower basic three pupils with visual impairments in the experimental and control groups in Gindiri, Plateau State.
2. Determine the phonics sequencing instruction programme on Braille writing skills of the lower basic three pupils with visual impairments in the experimental and control groups in Gindiri, Plateau State.

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses will guide the study and will be tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in phonics sequencing instruction programme mean scores on braille reading skills of pupils with visual impairments in the experimental and control groups in Gindiri, Plateau State.
2. There is no significant difference in the phonics sequencing instruction programme mean scores on braille writing skills of pupils with visual impairments in the experimental and control groups in Gindiri, Plateau State.

Methodology

Research Design

The study employed a true experimental research design. Specifically, the pretest-posttest control group design. True experimental research design allows the researcher to establish a cause-and-effect relationship between variables. The design is considered the most rigorous and reliable method for testing hypotheses and establishing causal relationships. The reason for using a true experimental design is that the design provides adequate and complete control for the source of internal validity.

Population and Sample

The population of this study was all lower basic three pupils in Gindiri School for the Blind. Data from the school showed that lower basic three have 10 pupils with visual impairments in the 2023/2024 academic session. The choice of this class was made because it is at this stage that blending of two and three-letter words is learnt.

Sample size

The sample size for this study was made up of all 10 pupils with visual impairments in lower basic three. The choice of ten (10) pupils with visual impairments as the sample size was informed by the fact that they were the only available pupils in the lower basic three with visual impairments in the school under study.

Sampling Technique

The sampling technique used was a simple random sampling method. The researcher assigned each pupil a unique random Braille number between 1 and 10 on Braille tiles. Pupils with odd numbers were in the experimental group, while those with even numbers were in the control group.

Instrument for Data Collection

The instrument used in this research for data collection was the Literacy Skills Acquisition Test (LSAT). This instrument was adapted by the researcher from Deshi (2018) on literacy skills. The original items were on print while the researcher transcribed the printed item into braille and embossed the pictures attached so that pupils with visual impairments are able to read and identify them tactually.

Description of the Instrument

The LSAT was divided into two sections, 1 and 2. Section 1 gave information on the Bio data of respondents, such as class, school, and age of onset. Section 2 consists of parts A and B, which measured the respondents' reading and writing skills. The LSAT covered four literacy skills, which had twenty-five items each. Pupils answered all the questions using their slate and stylus for a duration of one hour.

Validity

The instrument (Literacy Skills Acquisition Test (LSAT)) was adapted from Deshi (2018). It was revalidated by three experts: one was an expert in the Research, Measurement, and Evaluation Unit, Department of Educational Foundations, and the other two experts were from the Special Education and Rehabilitation Sciences Department.

Reliability

The internal stability reliability was established using the Cronbach-Alpha Method. This was done during a pilot study when the instrument was tried out on a sample different from the one for the main study. The data collected was used in estimating the reliability of the LSAT to measure the internal stability of the items.

Procedure for Data Collection

The researcher employed the assistance of two researchers from the school under study to administer the intervention alongside the researcher. The intervention programme: Phonics Sequencing Instruction Programme (PSIP) was an eight-week programme developed on reading and Braille writing skills. It also consists of Phonics Tips (Phonics Sequencing), read aloud, discussions, and plenary sessions.

Method Of Data Analysis

The data collected from the field was analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Research questions were answered using means and standard deviations. The hypotheses were tested using ANOVA. Inferential statistics of Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to test the two postulated hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance

Hypothesis One

There was no significant difference in phonics sequencing instruction programme mean scores in Braille reading of lower basic three pupils with visual impairments in the experimental and control groups.

Table 1: ANOVA Summary of Phonics Sequence Instruction Programme Mean Scores in Braille Reading of the Lower Basic Three Pupils with Visual Impairments in the Experimental and Control Groups

Source	Dependent Variable	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p-value
Corrected Model	Pre-Test Reading	.900 ^a	1	.900	.474	.511
	Post-Test Reading	115.600 ^b	1	115.600	38.533	.000
Intercept	Pre-Test Reading	2044.900	1	2044.900	1076.263	.000
	Post-Test Reading	3168.400	1	3168.400	1056.133	.000
GROUPS	Pre-Test Reading	.900	1	.900	.474	.511
	Post-Test Reading	115.600	1	115.600	38.533	.000
Error	Pre-Test Reading	15.200	8	1.900		
	Post-Test Reading	24.000	8	3.000		
Total	Pre-Test Reading	2061.000	10			
	Post-Test Reading	3308.000	10			

Note: GROUPS mean between the Experimental and Control Groups

Table 1 shows the ANOVA of the Phonics Sequencing Instruction Programme in Reading Skills

of Lower Basic Three Pupils in the Experimental and Control groups. The Pretest Reading skills $F(1, 10) = 0.474$, P-value of 0.511. Since the P-value of 0.511 was greater than the 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was accepted. It was concluded that there was no significant difference in the pretest Reading skill between pupils in the experimental and Control groups. The Post-test Reading skills $F(1, 10) = 38.533$, P-value of 0.000. Since the P-value of 0.000 was less than the 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected. It was concluded that there was a significant difference in the post-test Reading skills between pupils in the experimental and Control groups. This implied that the phonics sequencing instruction programme significantly improved the reading skills of pupils in the experimental group differently.

Hypothesis Two

There was no significant difference in phonics sequencing instruction programme mean scores in Braille writing of the lower basic three pupils with visual impairments in the experimental and control groups.

Table 2: ANOVA Summary of Phonics Sequence Instruction Programme Mean Scores in Braille Writing Skills of Lower Basic Three Pupils with Visual Impairments in the Experimental and Control Groups

Source	Dependent Variable	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p-value
Corrected Model	Pre-Test Writing	.900 ^a	1	.900	.225	.648
	Post-Test Writing	122.500 ^b	1	122.500	27.528	.001
Intercept	Pre-Test Writing	1988.100	1	1988.100	497.025	.000
	Post-Test Writing	3132.900	1	3132.900	704.022	.000
GROUPS	Pre-Test Writing	.900	1	.900	.225	.648
	Post-Test Writing	122.500	1	122.500	27.528	.001
Error	Pre-Test Writing	32.000	8	4.000		
	Post-Test Writing	35.600	8	4.450		
Total	Pre-Test Writing	2021.000	10			
	Post-Test Writing	3291.000	10			

Note: GROUPS mean between the Experimental and Control Groups

Table 2 shows the ANOVA on the phonics sequencing instruction programme mean scores in Braille writing skills of the lower basic three pupils in the experimental and control groups. The Pretest Braille writing skills $F(1, 10) = 0.225$, P-value of 0.648. Since the P-value of 0.648 is greater than the 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was accepted. It was concluded that there was no significant difference in the pretest writing skills between pupils in the experimental and Control groups. The Post-test literacy skills $F(1, 10) = 27.58$, P-value of 0.001. Since the P-value of 0.001 was less than the 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected. It was concluded that there was a significant difference in the post-test writing skills of pupils in the experimental and Control groups. This implies that the phonics sequencing instruction programme significantly improves the Braille writing skills of pupils in the experimental group differently.

Conclusion

Literacy skills are the umbrella block under which the study is located. Pupils with visual impairments are not taught literacy skills adequately, as teachers are not sufficiently equipped to effectively teach these pupils, mainly as a result of knowledge gaps in doing so. The major contribution of the study to knowledge is the utilization of a phonics sequencing instruction programme on literacy skills acquisition of pupils with visual impairment in Mangu, Plateau State, Nigeria. The study established that the phonics sequencing instruction programme was effective in enhancing and improving the literacy skills of pupils with visual impairments.

The findings of this study have several implications for pupils with visual impairment in lower basic schools, parents of pupils with visual impairments, special education teachers/rehabilitation scientists, regular teachers, head teachers, curriculum developers, and researchers as a whole. The findings revealed that literacy skills for the lower basic three pupils with visual impairments at the pre-test of the experimental and control groups were the same. At the post-test, however, the literacy skills of the experimental group were higher than those of the control group due to the provision of phonics sequencing instruction programme opportunities. Therefore, the phonics sequencing instruction programme is deemed effective in improving the reading and writing of pupils with visual impairments. It opens up a world of possibilities, empowering them to access information, express themselves, and navigate the world independently.

Recommendations

In view of findings from the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Pupils with visual impairment should be provided with specific and timely feedback through the use of Literacy Skills Acquisition Test (LSAT) to support their learning and build efficacy by bringing the pupils into the process of their own learning.
2. Teachers and parents of pupils with visual impairment should use phonics sequencing instruction programme to help improve literacy skills of pupils with visual impairment.
3. Head teachers of schools for children with visual impairment should encourage the use of phonics sequencing instruction programmes as a therapy to improve literacy skills of pupils with visual impairment.
4. Future researchers should carry out a similar study in other parts of the country using a different class level of lower basic school pupils with a larger sample to determine pupils' literacy skills using a phonics sequencing instruction programme.
5. Curriculum developers and the Government should include phonics sequencing instruction programmes in the literacy skills curriculum of pupils with visual impairment.

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